

Dataset

behavior_performance.mat (Figure 1)

- Matrix of delayed-response task correct rate (animal × session)
 - o Female animal 3, 5 and 7; male animal 1, 2, 4 and 6

matched_dataset.mat (Figure 1, 4 and 6)

- Pre-processed dataset of activity of neurons that were matched across learning.
- Variables with structure {learning stage}{session} with 3 learning stages (naive: 1; intermediate: 2; expert: 3) and 13 sessions.
 - o e.g. data.activity.raw_left_trial_activity{3}{13} (trial × time × cell)
- Variables with structure {learning stage} with 3 learning stages (naive: 1; intermediate: 2; expert: 3), all cells concatenated across all sessions and animals.
 - o e.g. data.AUC.choice_select_concat_stim_left_trial_auc{3}, cells concatenated across all sessions (1 × cell)

cortical_area_boundaries.mat (Figure 3, 4 and 6)

- Variables required to plot the cortical map.

non_matched_dataset.mat (Figure 2 and 3)

- Pre-processed dataset of activity of neurons that were not matched across learning.
- Variables with structure {animal}{session} with 7 animals and 6 sessions (naive: 1 and 2; intermediate: 3 and 4; expert: 5 and 6).
 - o e.g. data.all_SessionData{7}{6}
- Variables with structure {animal}{session}{region} with 7 animals, 6 sessions and 8 regions (ALM: 1; M1a: 2; M1p: 3; M2: 4; S1fl: 5; vS1: 6; RSC: 7; PPC: 8).
 - o e.g. data.all_choice_mode_GS{7}{6}{8} (trial × time)

decoding_accuracy.mat (Figure 5)

- Pre-processed dataset after running “get_retained_eliminated_activity()” for intermediate sessions.
- Variables with structure {learning stage}{session} with 1 learning stage and 13 sessions.
 - o e.g. decoding_accuracy.auc_retained{2}{10} (cell × shuffle)
- Variables with structure {learning stage}{region} with data concatenated across sessions with 1 learning stage and 8 regions (ALM: 1; M1a: 2; M1p: 3; M2: 4; S1fl: 5; vS1: 6; RSC: 7; PPC: 8).
 - o e.g. decoding_accuracy.region_concat_retained_auc{2}{8} (1 × cell)

retained_elim_data.mat (Figure 5)

- Pre-processed dataset after running “get_decoding_accuracy()”.
- Variables with structure {session}{learning stage} with 2 learning stages (naive: 1; intermediate: 2) and 13 sessions.
 - o e.g. retained_elim_data.reconstructed_activity.reshaped_retained_naive_predicted_activity{13}{2} (cell × trial × time × shuffle)

retained_eliminated_data_raw.mat (Figure 5)

- Dataset used with $\alpha = 0.95$ to run “get_decoding_accuracy()”.

ablated_data.mat (Figure 6)

- Pre-processed dataset for expert sessions after running “get_ablated_data()”. Population activity projected to choice axis for control and ablated reconstructed activity.
- Variables with structure {source region, target region}{learning stage}{session} with 8 source and target regions (ALM: 1; M1a: 2; M1p: 3; M2: 4; S1fl: 5; vS1: 6; RSC: 7; PPC: 8), 1 expert learning stage and 14 sessions.
 - o e.g. ablated_data.choice_mode.concat_control_right_choice_mode{8,8}{1}{14} (trial × time × shuffle)

ablated_data_raw.mat (Figure 6)

- Dataset to run “get_ablated_data()”
- Activity of neurons that were not matched across learning.

- Variables with structure {session}{learning stage} with 14 sessions and 3 learning stages (naive: 1; intermediate: 2; expert: 3).

optogenetics_data.mat (Figure 7)

- Raw data from Bpod for PPC and vS1 sessions.
- Variables with structure (animal, session) with 5 animals and 6 sessions (trained: session 1-3; over-trained: session 4-6).

DREADD_data.mat (Figure 7)

- Raw data from Bpod for CNO and saline sessions.
- Variables with structure (animal, session) with 6 animals and 3 sessions.

DREADD_activity.mat (Figure 7)

- Deconvolved neural activity for CNO and saline sessions.
- Variables with structure {animal}{session} with 5 animals and 6 sessions.
 - o e.g. DREADD_activity.cno.activity.all_resp{2}{3} (cell × trial × time)

RNN_demo

- Demo of 2 trained RNNs, +PPC and +vS1, for run_RNN_demo.m.
- Variables L, R and L_pos corresponding to the output of the trained network during left, right and left with distractor trials, respectively (trial × unit × time).

GLM_demo

- Demo data for an example session and region required to train GLM and process GLM output.

example_bpod_data.mat

- Demo behavior data from Bpod.

example_roimatchpub.mat

- Demo indices of cells matched across naive, intermediate and expert sessions using RoiMatchPub.

example_suite2p_data.mat

- Demo neural activity data for one session from one region.

example_wavesurfer_data.mat

- Demo behavior data from wavesurfer (e.g. trial onset, lick onset).

DLC

- Demo .csv files consisting of *x* and *y* coordinates of the left and right forelimb from DeepLabCut.

TrialOnsetVector.mat

- Demo variable containing a vector of trial onset for mouse behavior videos.